

THE PURPOSE, OBJECTIVES, CONTENT AND CONDITIONS OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: For a long time, the fundamental goal of children's speech development was considered to be the development of the ability to express an independent thought in an oral statement by independent efforts (K.D. Ushinsky). The fulfillment of this goal was associated with the correct pronunciation of sounds and words; the correct use of words in meaning; the correct change of layers according to the grammar of the Russian language.

Keywords: tasks of speech development, content of speech development work, speech development program, preschool children.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, along with the correctness of speech, its communicative expediency is also distinguished. The correctness of speech is characterized by the fact that the speaker uses language units in accordance with the norms of the language, and the communicative expediency of speech is considered as the optimal use of language in specific communication conditions. The goal of speech development of preschool children has also changed. It provides not only the formation of skills and abilities of correct speech, but also the formation of skills and abilities of accurate, expressive speech, free and appropriate use of language units, compliance with the rules of speech etiquette, taking into account the age

characteristics and capabilities of children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Currently, the main goal of speech development of preschool children is the formation of their oral speech and the culture of verbal communication with others on the basis of mastering the literary language of their people. A number of specific, special tasks follow from the general goal of speech development of preschool children. These include: the formation of a dictionary, the education of the sound culture of speech, the formation of the grammatical structure of speech, the development of coherent speech (dialogical (colloquial) and monologue), the formation of elementary awareness of the phenomena of language and speech, the education of interest and love for the artistic word. The main tasks of speech development are given throughout preschool childhood, while at each age stage their gradual complication is carried out. The content of speech tasks is determined by linguistic concepts and psychological features of language acquisition. Let's briefly focus on the characteristics of each task.

1. Dictionary formation.

In the general system of work on the development of speech in kindergarten, the enrichment of the dictionary, its consolidation and activation occupy a very large place. The word is the basic unit of the language, and improving speech communication is impossible without expanding the child's vocabulary. Mastering the vocabulary of the native language by preschool children is the basis of their speech development. Vocabulary work in kindergarten is carried out on the basis of familiarization with the surrounding life. It is closely related to the cognitive development of children. At the same time, cognitive development, the development of conceptual thinking is impossible without the assimilation of new

words expressing the concepts assimilated by the child, consolidating the new knowledge and ideas received by him. The formation of the vocabulary of preschoolers in kindergarten involves working on the word as a unit of language, in particular on the ambiguity of the word. The disclosure of the semantic richness of a polysemous word plays an important role in the formation of the accuracy of word usage. The main thing in the development of a children's dictionary is the development of the meanings of words and their appropriate use in accordance with the context of the utterance, with the situation in which communication takes place.

2. Education of the sound culture of speech.

Mastering the sound system of a language is the basis for the formation of a child's speech and "includes two interrelated processes: the formation of a child's perception of the sounds of language, or, as it is called, phonemic hearing, and the formation of the pronunciation of speech sounds." Preschool children master the sound culture of speech in the process of communicating with people around them. The teacher has a great influence on the formation of speech culture in children. It helps preschool children to master the correct speech breathing, the correct pronunciation of all the sounds of their native language, clear pronunciation of words, the ability to use their voice, teaches children to speak slowly, intonationally expressively. Developing correct, well-sounding speech in children, the teacher must solve the following tasks: to educate children's speech hearing, gradually developing its main components; to form the pronunciation side of speech; to develop the pronunciation of words according to the norms of orthoepy of the Russian literary language; to educate intonational expressiveness of speech. Teaching children the intonation pattern of an utterance is aimed at developing the ability to convey not only the semantic meaning of the utterance, but also its emotional features.

3. Formation of the grammatical structure of speech.

This task involves the formation of the morphological side of speech (changing words by gender, numbers, cases), methods of word formation and syntax (mastering different types of phrases and sentences). Children learn the grammatical structure practically by imitating the speech of adults and language generalizations. Conditions for mastering difficult grammatical forms, developing grammatical skills and abilities, and preventing grammatical errors are created in the preschool education institution. Attention is drawn to the development of all parts of speech, the development of different ways of word formation, a variety of syntactic constructions. It is important to ensure that children freely use grammatical skills and abilities in speech communication, in coherent speech.

4. Development of coherent speech.

The development of coherent speech is one of the fundamental tasks of speech education of preschool children. It is in coherent speech that the main function of language and speech is realized - communicative (communication). It shows all the achievements of the child in mastering the native language, and the relationship between mental and speech development is most pronounced.

The level of development of coherent speech reflects all other tasks of speech development: the formation of a dictionary, grammatical structure, phonetic side.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the process of familiarizing children with fiction, the teacher forms such elementary skills in preschool children as: listening and understanding works of art, expressing judgments about their heroes. Children master the ability to retell small artistic texts, memorize and expressively recite by heart small poems

available in content. Preschoolers enrich their vocabulary, develop figurative speech, poetic hearing, creative speech activity, aesthetic and moral concepts are formed. The identification of speech development tasks is conditional; they are closely related to each other in working with children. The interrelation of different speech tasks on the basis of an integrated approach to their solution creates prerequisites for the most effective development of speech skills and abilities.

The purpose and objectives of children's speech development are reflected in the curriculum of preschool education in the educational field "Speech development and communication culture". The curriculum is based on data from psychology and related sciences on the child's mastery of oral speech, which determines the scope and sequence of requirements for children at different age levels. The program is also built taking into account the most important pedagogical position on the leading role of activity in the development of the child; its material is correlated with various types of children's activities (play, classes, etc.).

CONCLUSION

The preschool curriculum (the educational field "Speech development and communication culture") was created taking into account the main didactic principles of systematicity and interrelation of educational material, its concreteness and accessibility, it traces the concentricity in the formation of children's speech skills (i.e., the passage of the same sections at each age stage with gradual expansion and deepening their contents). All tasks and requirements in the program are outlined briefly. Only the general requirements for the knowledge and skills of children are clearly named. The teacher should be able to specify each general requirement of the program. The conditions for the implementation of the curriculum are: the correct organization of children's life in a preschool institution, communication, classroom instruction, cultural developing

speech environment, the availability of didactic equipment.

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